

PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: this article provides feedback on the pedagogical-psychological features of the social development and activity of young people.

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In addition to the fact that the comprehensive maturation of the younger generation is the main factor in ensuring the development of society, it also occupies a leading place in its social activation as a person. The social activity of the youth personality is important according to the following two aspects: firstly, it creates the ground for the individual to find his place in society, and secondly, his knowledge, strength, opportunity and talent are directed to work towards the development of society.

Analysis of sources shows that in a democratic society, youth social activity does not arise on its own, but is formed as a result of pedagogical activity, which is carried out purposefully in a regular way. The provision of theoretical and practical knowledge to young people, the formation of skills and competencies of social activity in them, is relevant in that it also has its own significance for the theory and practice of pedagogy.

Theoretical sources on the problem, as well as the results of the study of its practical State, showed the existence of a number of contradictions in this area. In

particular – - the imbalance between the modern requirements for the social activity of young people in the democratic process and their knowledge, skills and qualifications, competencies of existing social activity; – the fact that the social activity of young people does not occur spontaneously, but is formed as a result of the pedagogical activity carried out constantly, and this process is not considered as a pedagogical system with a research and analytical orientation; -young people, there are a number of specific features and factors of social activation that are not sufficiently studied; - the presence of the need for the application of scientifically based effective forms, tools and methods of the pedagogical process aimed at increasing the social activity of young people means that research in this direction will be of importance. In the effective implementation of this task, the search for forms, tools, methods and methods in which the characteristics and conditions of a socially active person are composed, in turn, a deep understanding of the essence of the concepts of "youth", "social activity", is a very important issue, both in theory and from the practical side. In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word "Young" is given as "1. The years lived from the time of birth are a total of; life expectancy. 2. Stage in the life of a person or animal, period, life.

As a personality-specific manifestation of activity, activity occurs, which is differentiated from behavior by its psychological symptoms. Any activity is a process expression consisting of goals and results. The conscious implementation of activities is the driving force of society and the condition of living. The concept of activity as a principle of worldview has been decided since the development of German classical philosophy. During this period, conditions were created in European culture to view the individual as the basis and principles inherent in the multifaceted direction of intelligence, activity and initiative. Such a view was taken by the German philosopher I.Kant started. The needs of living beings in existence in their own way and in a certain direction, encouraging behavior with a certain degree of force, act as a source of activity for them. Thinking based on psychological sources,"...need is expressed in a state - of-the-art way in which a

living being expresses its subordination to these and manifests its activity in relation to these conditions". And human activity is manifested in the process of satisfaction of these needs. Needs-demand, need for what is necessary to maintain the life activity of the organism, human personality, Social Group, society as a whole.

Depending on the field of activity, there may be Labor, knowledge, communication; material, spiritual, depending on the object; individual (personal), group, collective, social needs, according to the subject. The human need is formed in the process of its upbringing, that is, by approaching and approaching the cultural process. Because the process of satisfying a person's own needs is distinguished as an active, specific goal-oriented process of acquiring a form of activity determined by social progress. Therefore, various aspects of this problem are studied in pedagogical science. A person becomes a spiritually harmonious person only when he perceives his social obligations, his duty to society, his responsibility as a natural state, as an integral part of his freedom and social activity. The activity of a person is the main factor in its formation as a person. During this process, not only adaptation to the natural and social world occurs, but also a person changes it to his liking. The society itself, its system and structure, the factors that make up the relationship in it – all this is the result of the activity of the individual based on creativity. Activity, activity means the manifestation of the forces that make up the essence of a person's personality. As the world changes, the active person at the same time continuously improves his abilities, knowledge, skills and skills. He realizes his identity as such, manifests himself in society as an active person. In this, the range of human needs is expanding, and at the same time a qualitative and numerical increase in the means of satisfying these needs occurs. The activity of a person is formed under the influence of social environment and material factors. Where there is no activity, the individual does not develop and its possibilities do not come true. The activity of the individual is composed in a pedagogical process aimed at a specific goal. Trends in the development of

personality activity are realized in the process of work, study, play, communication. Each person enters into a social relationship with the members of society. It is known that the concept of "activity" is confused with the concept of activity in some cases, in particular in the fields of science researching the individual and his activity. For example, in a dictionary on "Psychology", this concept is manifested in the fact that "a common feature of living matter, tevarak, interacts with the surrounding environment.

Psychic activity is characterized by this interaction, activity on this basis," - says the author. "Social activity-increased participation of social entities in socio-political processes, increased labor and cultural activity, striving to fully realize the rights and duties established by law," the scientific-popular dictionary of independence describes. The encyclopedic dictionary from "political science" interprets personality activism as a way of political activism. In this dictionary, activity is explained as follows: "personality activity is clearly manifested in the attitude towards objective reality. This attitude is that the more freely each individual has a position in society, the more freely involved in social relations towards meeting his diverse needs, the more it affects the growth of his political activism", says the secretary.

The analysis of the accumulated experiences in this field in our country shows that in a democratic society, social activity of young people does not arise on its own, but is formed as a result of pedagogical activity, which is carried out purposefully in a regular way. The provision of theoretical and practical knowledge to young people, the formation of skills and competencies of social activity in them, is relevant in that it also has its own significance for the theory and practice of pedagogy. Austrian psychologist and philosopher V. Frankl argues that the importance of individuality, the dignity and content of the human individual all the time depend on the society in which he lives. American sociologist T. Parkinson believes that genuine personal dignity is expressed in a person's relationship with the enveloping environment, that is, in his activity.

Psychologists R.Plomin and X.The Hermans (1997) argue that in fact, the full-fledged, harmonious formation of a person is influenced by three main factors: 1. Biological possibilities that exist in an individual – in this case, the influence of temperament type on the processes of human interaction is implied. 2. Subjective, that is, psychological capabilities of the individual – in this, these opportunities form a strategy of the process of interpersonal relations, personally choose to engage in interaction, and complement and improve them in social marriage. 3. Direct interpersonal relations are the process itself, which is carried out in a social cultural environment. The social cultural environment ensures the formation of the individual as the main mechanism for interpersonal relationships.

In the process of interpersonal relations, it is advisable to help young people realize intellectual opportunities in themselves. This situation confirms that social and intellectual development has been observed to increase not only in these young people, but also in their peers. G.K.Selevko distinguishes between two levels of activity. The first, lower level – determines the productive, acting, regenerative activity of a person to a certain extent, in which a person plays the role of a more manageable object. Activities at this level are known as "object activities". The second, higher level of activity-the primary reason for the activities of the learner, playing the role of the source, has a creative, transformative quality. In this, the person carrying out the activity is a subject, and his will is involved in the activity ("subject activity"). There have been many studies done in the field of studying personality social activity. Including L.I.Amanbaeva" civil education of young people in a new social context", A.A.Savastina and L.B.Osipova's "youth social activity-as a condition for the dynamic development of society", V.A.Sitarov and V.G.Maralov's" social activity of the individual"," fundamentals of preschool education and the formation of social activity in children of small school age", S.Yu.In such works as Korolkova "youth social activism", the theoretical foundations, practical areas of social activism are somewhat revealed. V.S.According to Merlin, the self-awareness of an individual is based on: 1) self-

awareness as it is; 2) positive acceptance of one's "Me" by an individual; 3) understanding what kind of mental character and spiritual and moral qualities one has; 4) self-imposed socio-moral assessments, awareness of their level. At the moment, the scientific research of our contemporary scientists, who carried out scientific research in different directions and topics from pedagogical, philosophical, psychological and various points of view within the framework of this problem, also stimulated the birth of this research, providing specific support in solving the problems posed in it. In Particular, M. Makhmudova, G.J. Tulenova, T.Egamberdieva, CA.Q. Quranboev, I.R. In the scientific research of such scientists as Safarbuvaeva, the problems of social activity and activation of personality are highlighted in pedagogical, psychological and philosophical terms. In Particular, M. In the scientific research of makhmudova, issues of raising social activity in young people of younger age are substantiated. The researcher concluded that the following conditions are sufficient grounds for ensuring the effectiveness of the process of forming the social activity of young people of small school age.

Based on the study of the content of research in various fields carried out on the problems of the development of youth social activity, we came to the following conclusions: 1. The justification of the content of increasing the social activity of young people, the development of its methodology is an important task before the science and practice of pedagogy. 2. It is noted that increasing the social activity of young people is important in ensuring the general maturity of the individual and the social development of society, which until today has not been researched as a holistic pedagogical process. 3. The social activity of young people depends on their participation in the process of social relations, which determines the attitude of the individual to social being. In the early days when the Republic of Uzbekistan gained socio-political independence, the task was put on the agenda to promote the ideas of independence among the population of the country, including young people, to decide on social activity aimed at strengthening independence in them.

The role of the educational process in the successful solution of tasks in this regard is great. In the context of the rapid development of Science and technology, the increase in competition in the global world, each state and society will depend on the intellectual development of young people on the basis of their competitiveness in this process, as well as on the full implementation of their talents and abilities. Therefore, this issue is always reflected in all strategies aimed at ensuring the long-term development of states. The strategy of action of the Republic of Uzbekistan on five priority areas of development in 2017-2021 was no exception in this regard. In it, a separate department is dedicated to improving the youth policy of the state. It covers a number of priorities aimed at improving the effectiveness of state policy on Youth, which is 10 million citizens of Uzbekistan or 31% of the country's population. In this regard, the need to establish the Youth Union of Uzbekistan was determined by life itself, which requires the organization to solve the most pressing issues in youth life, especially to create suitable conditions for unorganized youth to find their place in life, to comprehensively apply young people, to provide vocational guidance and employment, to encourage their initiatives. It is also very symbolic that the day of the formation of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan - June 30-will be announced as Youth Day. The reason is that this union becomes a structure that, with state bodies, NGOs and other institutions of civil society, provides effective activities in the implementation of the state's youth policy, carries out professional activities under the slogan "youth – builder of the future".

It should be noted that a number of specific measures are being implemented in the country aimed at stimulating the activity of young people in socio-political life. The above makes it possible to say that a direction has been established in Uzbekistan to strengthen the place of youth in social and political life. In this regard, special attention is paid to the full support of youth initiatives from state and youth organizations. Relying on this, it can be noted that young people occupy a special place at a new stage in the development of Uzbekistan.

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